

Supplementary appendix S3: pooled results of forest plot in CGI-S/WHOQOL-BREF/TESS scores and number of participants who decreased antidepressants dosage

Figure 1. MA/EA plus antidepressants versus antidepressants alone on the CGI-S score

Figure 2. MA/EA plus antidepressants versus antidepressants alone on the WHOQOL-BREF score

Figure 3. MA/EA plus antidepressants versus antidepressants alone on the TESS score

Figure 4. Acupuncture plus antidepressants versus antidepressants alone on the number of participants who decreased antidepressants dosage